

COMMON BACTERIA AND THEIR ANTIBIOTIC SENSITIVITY IN NEONATAL SEPSIS

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Abstract

Objective:

To determine the frequency of positive blood cultures in suspected neonatal sepsis and to identify the bacterial isolates and their corresponding antibiotic sensitivities.

Methods:

This cross-sectional study was conducted in Department of Pediatrics of DHQ Hospital, Sargodha from May-2024 to January-2025. This study included 149 neonates, aged between 1 to 28 days, admitted with suspicion of sepsis. Blood samples were obtained and sent to hospital laboratory for determination of culture positive sepsis and to determine the microbial and antibiotic susceptibility patterns.

Results:

The outcomes of the study depict that average age of the participants was 14.2 (± 8.3) days. Positive blood cultures were found in 35 (23.5%) participants. Regarding bacterial isolates, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* was the most prevalent, accounting for 21 (60.0%) isolates while, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was identified in 6 (17.1%) isolates. Moreover, ampicillin demonstrated a high susceptibility rate of 94.3%, with 33 isolates showing sensitivity. Similarly, gentamycin also exhibited substantial efficacy, with 85.7% of the cases responding favorably. Likewise, meropenem was effective in 71.4% of isolates.

Conclusion:

In the current investigation, it was observed that 23.5% of sepsis cases were confirmed through positive culture results. Typically, the initial empiric antimicrobial treatments advocated by the World Health Organization, namely ampicillin and gentamicin, showed strong effectiveness against the majority of the microorganisms identified in these cases.

INTRODUCTION

The neonatal period represents a critical time in life, characterized by a heightened vulnerability to infections. This susceptibility arises from an immature immune system, insufficient exposure to pathogens, and limited production of immunoglobulins.¹ Consequently, infections are ranked among the top causes of infant mortality on a global scale. Neonatal sepsis poses a major health issue, particularly in developing nations, where it constitutes a leading factor in both morbidity and mortality rates. Each year, approximately 3 million cases of neonatal sepsis are reported, with mortality rates ranging from 11% to 19%.² The World Health Organization (WHO) highlights that bacterial infections are the primary culprits behind neonatal infections, contributing to over 550,000 deaths annually.³ In countries with limited resources, sepsis is connected to 30% to 50% of all neonatal fatalities.⁴

Sepsis-related fatalities are largely preventable when diagnoses are made promptly and treatment with appropriate antimicrobial agents is administered swiftly.⁵ However, there is a significant gap due to the absence of rapid and reliable diagnostic tools capable of identifying the specific pathogens responsible for sepsis.⁶ Currently, blood culture remains the primary diagnostic method, but it has limitations, including a sensitivity range of 50% to 80% and the requirement of several hours to days to produce results.⁷ Consequently, initiating empirical antimicrobial therapy without definitive pathogen identification is crucial in suspected cases. Gaining detailed knowledge about the most common causative agents of neonatal sepsis and understanding their antimicrobial sensitivity profiles can help clinicians choose the most effective initial treatment regimens.⁸ The proposed study aimed to determine the frequency of positive blood cultures in suspected neonatal sepsis and to identify the bacterial isolates and their corresponding antibiotic sensitivities.

METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted in Department of Pediatrics of DHQ Hospital, Sargodha from May-2024 to January-2025. This study included 149 neonates (aged 1 to 28 days), who were admitted with suspicion of sepsis. While, those premature neonates were excluded from the study, who had birth

asphyxia or who were already taking antibiotics at the time of inclusion.

A written informed consent was taken from parents after explaining the purpose of study. Demographic data including age, gender, duration of symptoms, prematurity and low birth weight was noted. Complete history was taken and physical examination was done.

Antibiotic susceptibility testing using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method:

Prior to blood collection, the skin surface was disinfected using a 10% Povidone-iodine solution for two minutes, followed by a 0.5% Chlorhexidine solution for one minute. Blood samples, ranging from one to three milliliters, were obtained aseptically from a peripheral vein and transferred into BACTEC PedsPlus™ culture vials (manufactured by Becton Dickinson, Ireland). These vials were then incubated in an automated BACTEC system maintained at a temperature of $35 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for a duration of five days, in accordance with the manufacturer's guidelines. Microbiologists at the hospital conducted subcultures and identified the microorganisms involved. Antibiotic susceptibility testing was performed using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method. After drawing blood for culture, neonates were initiated on empirical intravenous therapy with Ampicillin and Amikacin, which are considered first-line treatments, until the culture results were available. If there was no clinical improvement, antibiotic regimens were adjusted based on the healthcare provider's judgment and the neonate's condition.

Statistical Analysis:

The data collection and analysis were carried out using SPSS version 22.0. Descriptive statistics, including means and standard deviations were computed for continuous variables such as age and disease duration. Categorical variables, such as gender, sepsis type (early or late onset), prematurity status, low birth weight, blood culture results, and antibiotic sensitivity patterns were summarized through frequency counts and percentages.

RESULTS:

The current findings illustrate that average age of the participants was 14.2 (± 8.3) days. The duration of symptoms prior to the assessment averaged 5.1 (± 2.6) days. Among the participants, 86 (57.7%) were male, while 63 (42.3%) were female. In terms of prematurity, 86 participants (57.7%) were classified as premature, whereas 63 (42.3%) were term. Regarding birth weight, 43 participants (28.8%) were identified as having low birth weight. The type of sepsis was categorized, revealing that 79 participants (53.0%) had early onset sepsis, while 70 participants (47.0%) had late onset sepsis. Positive blood cultures were found in 35 participants (23.5%), whereas 114 (76.5%) had negative results (Table 1).

Regarding bacterial isolates, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* was the most prevalent, accounting for 21 isolates, which represented 60.0% of the total. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was identified in 6 isolates, making up 17.1% of the findings. Additionally, *Enterobacter* was noted in 5 isolates, corresponding to 14.3%. *Escherichia coli* had a smaller presence, with only 2 isolates, or 5.7%. Finally, *Staphylococcus aureus* was found in just 1 isolate, representing 2.8% of the total samples analyzed (Table 2).

The antibiotic susceptibility pattern was analyzed, revealing distinct levels of effectiveness among various antibiotics. Ampicillin demonstrated a high susceptibility rate of 94.3%, with 33 isolates showing sensitivity. Gentamycin also exhibited substantial efficacy, with 85.7% of the cases responding favorably. Meropenem was effective in 71.4% of isolates, while Cefotaxime showed a moderate susceptibility rate of 60.0%. Clindamycin and Piperacillin/tazobactam had lower susceptibility rates, at 20.0% and 31.4%, respectively. Other antibiotics, such as Amikacin, showed 37.1% effectiveness, whereas Erythromycin exhibited a lower 14.3% response. The rates for antibiotics like Ceftriaxone and Cloxacillin were quite minimal, both at 2.8%. Notably, Cotrimoxazole and Cefixime showed no effective susceptibility, recorded at 0.0%. Ofloxacin also had no reported efficacy, while the findings for Teicoplanin and Vancomycin indicated effectiveness in 8.6% and 57.1% of the isolates, respectively. Overall, the pattern highlighted a range of susceptibility, emphasizing the importance of selecting appropriate antibiotics for treatment (Table 3).

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics.

Age (days)	14.2 \pm 8.3
Duration of Symptoms (days)	5.1 \pm 2.6
Gender (%)	
Male	86 (57.7%)
Female	63 (42.3%)
Prematurity (%)	
Yes	86 (57.7%)
No	63 (42.3%)
Low Birthweight (%)	
Yes	43 (28.8%)
No	106 (71.2%)
Type of Sepsis (%)	
Early Onset Sepsis	79 (53.0%)
Late Onset Sepsis	70 (47.0%)
Positive Blood Culture (%)	
Yes	35 (23.5%)
No	114 (76.5%)

Table 2. Frequency of Bacterial Isolates (N=35).

Staphylococcus epidermidis	21 (60.0%)
Staphylococcus Aureus	01 (2.8%)
Enterobacter	05 (14.3%)
E. Coli	02 (5.7%)
Pseudomonas Aeruginosa	06 (17.1%)

Table 3. Antibiotic Susceptibility Pattern.

Ampicillin	33 (94.3%)
Amikacin	13 (37.1%)
Ceftriaxone	01 (2.8%)
Cefotaxime	21 (60.0%)
Cotrimoxazole	0 (0.0%)
Clindamycin	07 (20.0%)
Cefixime:	0 (0.0%)
Cloxacillin	01 (2.8%)
Erythromycin	05 (14.3%)
Gentamycin	30 (85.7%)
Meropenem	25 (71.4%)
Nalidixic acid	01 (2.8%)
Ofloxacin	00 (0.0%)
Piperacillin/tazobactam	11 (31.4%)
Teicoplanin	03 (8.6%)
Vancomycin	20 (57.1%)

DISCUSSION:

Neonatal sepsis is a critical health issue characterized by high rates of both morbidity and mortality among affected infants. Effective treatment hinges on the prompt initiation of empiric antimicrobial therapy; however, this approach must be informed by up-to-date data on the local patterns of pathogen prevalence and their antimicrobial susceptibilities. Without such crucial information, there is a heightened risk of antibiotics being used inappropriately, which can lead to the development and spread of antibiotic-resistant bacteria. This resistance poses a serious obstacle to successful sepsis management and underscores the need for ongoing surveillance of microbial epidemiology.

The research revealed that approximately 23.5% of newborns suspected of having sepsis actually had confirmed bacterial infections. Similar prevalence rates were reported by Fang et al. from China (23.0%)⁹, Mhada et al. from Tanzania (24.0%),¹⁰

Acheampong et al. from Ghana (21.0%)¹¹ Pokhrel et al. from Nepal (20.5%)¹² and Reddy et al. from South Africa (11%).¹³

Moreover, the observed prevalence in this study was significantly lower than the rates documented in various countries. For instance, Ethiopia reports the rates ranging from 36.5% to 46.6% across multiple studies,^{14, 15} while, Zambia has a reported rate of 38%.¹⁶ Nigeria shows a higher prevalence at 49.6%,¹⁷ with Tanzania reporting as high as 72%,¹⁸ and Uganda at 59%.¹⁹ Variations in these rates can be explained by differences in regional hygiene standards, patterns of antibiotic use, and study methodologies. Furthermore, factors such as advancements in diagnostic techniques, alterations in hospital protocols, and seasonal fluctuations can all impact the rates of neonatal sepsis observed in different settings.

In the existing study, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* 9 (64%), was the most common isolate identified of all the bacteria. A comparable investigation conducted in Ghana revealed similar results, with *Staphylococcus epidermidis* emerging as the predominant pathogen in both early-onset sepsis (EOS) at 59.1% and late-onset sepsis (LOS) at 52.8% within a tertiary care facility. Literature suggests that pathogens responsible for EOS often originate from the mother's genital tract, particularly through vertical transmission during delivery. These findings imply that such organisms may be transmitted from the mother to the newborn during birth.²⁰

A research study conducted in Nepal focused on identifying bacteria present in a specific context. The findings showed that *Staphylococcus epidermidis* was the most prevalent, representing 57.3% of the samples. *Escherichia coli* was detected in 28.1% of cases, followed by *Staphylococcus aureus* at 11.2%, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* at a mere 1.1%.²¹

A study done in Ghana found that the prevalence of culture proven neonatal sepsis in was 17.3%. Gram positive organisms were the prevalent neonatal sepsis causing organisms in that study with, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* the most common isolate found in 62.9% cultures, followed by *Staphylococcus aureus* in 7.7% cultures. *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa* (15.4%) was the most common isolate among the gram negative organisms, *Enterobacter* species was isolated in 15.4%, with single isolates each of *Escherichia coli* (7.7%) and *Proteus mirabilis* 7.7 % in late onset neonatal sepsis. Generally, gram negative bacteria exhibit a better susceptibility rate to gentamicin (100% in *Proteus mirabilis*, 25% in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) and ceftriaxone (100% in *Proteus mirabilis*, 75% in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*), while gram positive organisms are more sensitive to ampicillin (100% in *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and 100% in *Staphylococcus aureus*) and gentamicin (57% in *Staphylococcus epidermidis* and 50% in *Staphylococcus Aureus*).²²

While, in a study conducted in Nepal, out of 516 specimens, bacterial growth was obtained in 56 specimens (10.8%). Among Gram-negative organisms, *Enterobacter* species was isolated in 8.9%, *Escherichia coli* in 8.9% and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in 7.1%. Among gram-positive bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* was isolated in 19.6% of the isolates, and

Staphylococci were isolated in 11.1% of the isolates. Gentamycin was sensitive in 88.8% of gram-negative *Acinetobacter* species, and cotrimoxazole was sensitive in 81.8% of *S. aureus*.²³

The current research is limited by a small sample size and its single-center setting. While the findings may not be broadly applicable, the primary goal of creating a comprehensive assessment of the predominant pathogenic isolates and their antibiotic susceptibility in cases of neonatal sepsis at our facility has been accomplished. This information can serve as a valuable resource for effectively implementing appropriate empiric antimicrobial treatments.

CONCLUSION:

In our study, we found that 23.5% of sepsis cases were confirmed through positive culture results. Typically, the initial empiric antimicrobial treatments advocated by the World Health Organization, namely ampicillin and gentamicin, showed strong effectiveness against the majority of the microorganisms identified in these cases.

REFERENCES

1. Shobowale EO, Solarin AU, Elikwu CJ, Onyedibe KI, Akinola IJ, Faniran AA. Neonatal sepsis in a Nigerian private tertiary hospital: Bacterial isolates, risk factors, and antibiotic susceptibility patterns. *Ann Afr Med.* 2017;16(2):52-8.
2. Glaser MA, Hughes LM, Jnah A, Newberry D. Neonatal Sepsis: A Review of Pathophysiology and Current Management Strategies. *Adv Neonatal Care.* 2021;21(1):49-60.
3. Luoto R, Jartti T, Ruuskanen O, Waris M, Lehtonen L, Heikkinen T. Review of the clinical significance of respiratory virus infections in newborn infants. *Acta Paediatr.* 2016;105(10):1132-9.
4. Sorsa A. Epidemiology of Neonatal Sepsis and Associated Factors Implicated: Observational Study at Neonatal Intensive Care Unit of Arsi University Teaching and Referral Hospital, South East Ethiopia. *Ethiop J Health Sci.* 2019;29(3):333-42.

5. Kim HI, Park S. Sepsis: Early Recognition and Optimized Treatment. *Tuberc Respir Dis (Seoul)*. 2019;82(1):6-14.
6. Confield LR, Black GP, Wilson BC, Lowe DJ, Theakstone AG, Baker MJ. Vibrational spectroscopic analysis of blood for diagnosis of infections and sepsis: a review of requirements for a rapid diagnostic test. *Anal Methods*. 2021;13(2):157-68.
7. Thakur S, Thakur K, Sood A, Chaudhary S. Bacteriological profile and antibiotic sensitivity pattern of neonatal septicaemia in a rural tertiary care hospital in North India. *Indian J Med Microbiol*. 2016;34(1):67-71.
8. Raturi A, Chandran S. Neonatal Sepsis: Aetiology, Pathophysiology, Diagnostic Advances and Management Strategies. *Clin Med Insights Pediatr*. 2024;18:11795565241281337.
9. Fang P, Gao K, Yang J, Li T, Gong W, Sun Q, et al. Prevalence of Multidrug-Resistant Pathogens Causing Neonatal Early and Late Onset Sepsis, a Retrospective Study from the Tertiary Referral Children's Hospital. *Infect Drug Resist*. 2023;16:4213-25.
10. Mhada TV, Fredrick F, Matee MI, Massawe A. Neonatal sepsis at Muhimbili National Hospital, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania; aetiology, antimicrobial sensitivity pattern and clinical outcome. *BMC Public Health*. 2012;12:904.
11. Acheampong EN, Tsiase JA, Afriyie DK, Amponsah SK. Neonatal Sepsis in a Resource-Limited Setting: Causative Microorganisms and Antimicrobial Susceptibility Profile. *Interdiscip Perspect Infect Dis*. 2022;2022:7905727.
12. Pokhrel B, Koirala T, Shah G, Joshi S, Baral P. Bacteriological profile and antibiotic susceptibility of neonatal sepsis in neonatal intensive care unit of a tertiary hospital in Nepal. *BMC Pediatr*. 2018;18(1):208.
13. Reddy K, Bekker A, Whitelaw AC, Esterhuizen TM, Dramowski A. A retrospective analysis of pathogen profile, antimicrobial resistance and mortality in neonatal hospital-acquired bloodstream infections from 2009-2018 at Tygerberg Hospital, South Africa. *PLoS One*. 2021;16(1):e0245089.
14. Weldu Y, Naizgi M, Hadgu A, Desta AA, Kahsay A, Negash L, et al. Neonatal septicemia at intensive care unit, Ayder Comprehensive Specialized Hospital, Tigray, North Ethiopia: Bacteriological profile, drug susceptibility pattern, and associated factors. *PLoS One*. 2020;15(6):e0235391.
15. Assemie MA, Alene M, Yismaw L, Ketema DB, Lamore Y, Petrucka P, et al. Prevalence of Neonatal Sepsis in Ethiopia: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Int J Pediatr*. 2020;2020:6468492.
16. Egbe FN, Cowden C, Mwananyanda L, Pierre C, Mwansa J, Lukwesa Musyani C, et al. Etiology of Bacterial Sepsis and Isolate Resistance Patterns in Hospitalized Neonates in Zambia. *Pediatr Infect Dis J*. 2023;42(10):921-6.
17. Peterside O, Pondei K, Akinbami FO. Bacteriological Profile and Antibiotic Susceptibility Pattern of Neonatal Sepsis at a Teaching Hospital in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. *Trop Med Health*. 2015;43(3):183-90.
18. Majigo M, Makupa J, Mwazyunga Z, Luoga A, Kisinga J, Mwamkoa B, et al. Bacterial Aetiology of Neonatal Sepsis and Antimicrobial Resistance Pattern at the Regional Referral Hospital, Dar es Salam, Tanzania; A Call to Strengthening Antibiotic Stewardship Program. *Antibiotics (Basel)*. 2023;12(4).
19. Zamarano H, Musinguzi B, Kabajulizi I, Manirakiza G, Guti W, Muhwezi I, et al. Bacteriological profile, antibiotic susceptibility and factors associated with neonatal Septicaemia at Kilembe mines hospital, Kasese District Western Uganda. *BMC Microbiol*. 2021;21(1):303.
20. Labi AK, Obeng-Nkrumah N, Bjerrum S, Enweronu-Laryea C, Newman MJ. Neonatal bloodstream infections in a Ghanaian Tertiary Hospital: Are the current antibiotic recommendations adequate? *BMC Infect Dis*. 2016;16(1):598.
21. Adhikari N, Shah PK, Acharya G, Vaidya KM. Bacteriological profile and associated risk factors of neonatal sepsis in Paropakar Maternity and Women's Hospital Thapathali, Kathmandu. *Nepal Med Coll J*. 2014;16(2-4):161-4.
22. Aku FY, Akweongo P, Nyarko K, Sackey S, Wurapa F, Afari EA, et al. Bacteriological profile and antibiotic susceptibility pattern of common

- isolates of neonatal sepsis, Ho Municipality, Ghana-2016. *Matern Health Neonatol Perinatol.* 2018;4:2.
23. Thapa S, Sapkota LB. Changing Trend of Neonatal Septicemia and Antibiotic Susceptibility Pattern of Isolates in Nepal. *Int J Pediatr.* 2019;2019:3784529.

